

BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF SOME 3D-METAL BIOCOMPLEXES

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Abstract. Biogenic elements are necessary for the normal functioning of the body. But their inorganic salts have a toxic effect on the body. Therefore, the synthesis of complex compounds of biogenic elements with biologically active organic ligands and the study of their biological activity are of great importance.

Keywords: biogenic elements, complex compounds, bicomplexes, chelates, toxicity.

It is important to suggest that one of the important requirements for biologically active substances is their high level of safety, as well as specific pharmacophysiological activity. For determining the effect of the central atom, the nature of its chelate environment and other parameters on the safety of complexes, it is necessary to preliminarily study the level of their acute toxicity (LD₅₀) with the participation of specialists in the relevant field [1]. Acute toxicity LD₅₀ (median lethal dose) determination experiments were conducted in vivariums fed with standard amounts of feed, with unlimited access to drinking water, weighing 19-21 g. 36 outbred white mice of both sexes were divided into 5 main groups and a control group, with 6 mice in each group. A single intravenous administration of the drugs was used. It is known that, according to the study data using this method, the complexes retain their original structure when determining their LD₅₀ value. The obtained results are compared with the results of other studies [2], obtained experimental data are presented in Table 1.

Based on the obtained results, it can be concluded that the toxicity level of the complexes mainly depends on the nature of the central atom, donor groups of metal-coordinated ligands, as well as differences in the nature of the primary (H₂PL-Acid or HSal-MemSCL) and secondary (acidic or MemSCL) ligands. For example, in the case of cobalt(II) complexes, the toxicity of substances increases in the following sequence:

Similarly, the dependence of the toxicity level of a substance on the composition has been studied for nickel(II) complexes, in which it is also observed for substances with copper as the central atom; the corresponding sequence is expressed in the following form:

and this can be considered as a serious influence of the nature of the central atom on the toxicity level of the complexes. It is important that for complexes of the type M(H₂PL-Acid)_nH₂O, as the toxicity level of the metals decreases, the complexes are sorted into the following row Co > Cu > Ni, M(H₂PL-AspH)(MemSCL) nH₂O in case Cu > Co > Ni.

M(H₂PL-GluH)(MemSCL)·nH₂O and in complexes corresponding to the formula, the order of biometals is different: Zn > Co > Ni.

Co(H₂PL-MemSCL)·nH₂O complex, and hydroxy complexes have a much lower level of toxicity compared to the Co(H₂PL-MemSCL)(MemSCL)· nH₂O complex (Table 1). Apparently,

this is the result of the influence of the chelate environment of the central atom on the level of toxicity of the complexes.

Table 1

Acute toxicity (LD50) of the main coordination compounds (median lethal dose)

Complexes	LD ₅₀ , mg/kg	LD ₅₀ metall-ionxisobida, mg/kg
Cu(H ₂ PL-AspH)(MemSCL)·H ₂ O	173	28,2
Cu(H ₂ PL-GluH)(MemSCL)·H ₂ O	160	27,3
Cu(HSal-MemS ⁺)(MemS ⁺)[CuCl ₄]	186	29,6
Cu(HSal-MemS ⁺)(MemS ⁺) ₂ [CuCl ₃]·H ₂ O	209	35,3
Co(H ₂ PL-AspH)(MemSCL)·2H ₂ O	69	8,2
Co(H ₂ PL-GluH)(MemSCL)·2H ₂ O	73	8,4
Co(HSal-MemS ⁺)(MemS ⁺)[CoCl ₄]	210	38.0
Co(HSal-MemS ⁺)(MemS ⁺) ₂ [CuCl ₃ 2H ₂ O]	221	40.8
Ni(H ₂ PL-AspH)·2H ₂ O	162	22,2
Ni(H ₂ PL-GluH)·3H ₂ O	216	31,0
Ni(H ₂ PL-AspH)(MemSCL)·4H ₂ O	234	47,2
Ni(H ₂ PL-GluH)(MemSCL)·2H ₂ O	113	16,2
Zn(H ₂ PL -AspH)·H ₂ O	45	7,4
Zn(H ₂ PL -GluH)·2H ₂ O	40	6,62

For example, M(MemSCL)·nH₂O complex M(H₂PL-MemSCL)(Acid)·nH₂O (M- Co(II) when going into a complex, the difference in Zn increases and depends on the change in the nature of the chelate environment of the central atom. Consequently, an increase in the number of oxygen atoms coordinated with the central atom increases the level of toxicity of the bicomplexes. Similarly, the dependence of LD₅₀ on the nature of coordinated donor ligands is also observed in the case of complexes containing the GluH ion as secondary ligands. The level of toxicity of the complexes [2N,3O] M(H₂PL- Acid)(MemSCL) nH₂O increases significantly when moving from a set of coordinated atoms to a set of [4O,N] M(H₂PL- MemSCL)(GluH) nH₂O. At the same time, as mentioned earlier, the presence of a hydroxyl group increases the safety of the substance.

While analyzing the antidote activity of coordination compounds, it was studied using the example of complexes containing cobalt-based amino alcohols. [2N,3O].

In the case of N-substituted derivatives, their properties have not been studied. In addition, there is no systematic information in the literature on the protective (defensive) effect of complexes against stress. Therefore, with the participation of specialists, the activity of a number of synthesized compounds in acute poisoning with organophosphorus compounds (phosalone) was studied.

For determining the effect of the nature of the metal forming the complex on the antidote activity and on the process of restoring the landscape of formed elements of the blood in anemia (a consequence of acute poisoning with fasolones).

Besides that, complexes of the type M(H₂PL-Acid)(MemSCL) nH₂O were studied. It was found that metal ions are arranged in the following sequence according to their degree of influence on the restoration of cholinesterase activity: Zn > Co > Ni. This sequence also affects the effect of the metal ion on reducing the inflammatory process, the effect of the metal on a sharp decrease in

leukocytosis (an increase in the number of leukocytes) is shown in Table 1. It is noteworthy that the studied complexes have erythropoietic (an increase in the number of erythrocytes) and hemoglobin-forming activity, more pronounced than that of zinc, cobalt and nickel. In order to study the influence of the nature of its chelate environment in So(II) complexes $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{PL-GluH})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (I) va $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{PL-AspH})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ antidote activity of the ingredients $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{PL-AspH})(\text{MemSCL})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ compared to the complex. According to [3], the nature of the chelate environment of the central atom in the state of complex 1 corresponds to the set [N,3O] in the state of a solid aggregate, and [2N,2O] -in water solution. For complex 2, the following set of coordinated atoms is determined: in the solid state, and in an aqueous solution- the set is presented as [N,3O].

According to the parameters of the cholinesterase reactivation process, anti-inflammatory and erythropoietic indicators, cobalt complexes are arranged in the following order: this sequence indicates an increase in antidote activity in the case of complexes consisting of Schiff bases. In addition, a comparison of the antidote activity of the last two compounds shows that with an increase in the number of oxygen atoms, the specific activity of the substances decreases, which also corresponds to the literature data known to us [4, 5]. Accordingly, the correlation between the specific activity of a substance and the level of toxicity can be explained by the fact that complexes with a higher level of toxicity can bind more quickly and effectively to the biological systems of the body and affect various biological processes in a unique way $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{PL-AspH})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} > \text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{PL-GluH})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} > \text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{PL-GluH})(\text{MemSCL})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

REFERENCES

1. Bellamy JI. New data on IR spectra of complex molecules. Moscow: Mir, 1999. – P.318.
2. Kadirov MA, Anvarzhanov UM, Shadmanova KK Study of antidote activity of cobalt(II) complexes with vitamin U // Proceedings of the conf. "Pharmacy: science, education, innovation and production" Tashfarmi 2017. P. 336-337.
3. Kostromina NA, Kumok VN, Skorik NA Chemistry of coordination compounds. Moscow: Higher. school, 1990. – P.432.
4. Kriss EF, Volchenskova II, Grigorieva AS Coordination compounds in medicine. Kyiv: Nauk, Dumka, 1986. – P.216.
5. Skalny A. V., Rudakov I. A. Bioelements in medicine. Moscow: Publishing house "ONIX 21st century": Mir, 2004. P.272.